

OVERCOMING ORGANIZATIONAL INERTIA: HOW MANUFACTURING SMEs IMPLEMENT DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGY

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

The purpose of this study is to understand how manufacturing SMEs in emerging markets implement the DT strategy by managing change in their routines. The routines and inertia lens, which is considered a key concept in change management in manufacturing organizations, is applied. The research questions that this study seeks to answer are:

- 1) How do routines and inertia interact with DT strategy implementation?
- 2) How can a firm overcome inertia and successfully implement a DT strategy?

Both academics and practitioners can benefit from studying digital transformation. This is due to three major reasons. First, digital transformation (DT) is defined as organizational change triggered and shaped by the widespread adoption of digital technologies (Hanelt et al., 2020). This viewpoint allows us to conceptually comprehend the DT phenomenon and its management in business practice, drawing on the vast and varied body of knowledge in the literature on organizational change and innovation (Poole & Van de Ven, 2004). Second, DT goes beyond the introduction of digital technology and changes the business model itself. It is a strategic change that alters how a business creates value and operates (Singh et al., 2020). Thirdly, and most importantly for practitioners, DT is a difficult task to achieve. It is a complex issue that affects most or all business units. Organizations need to address the journey of DT on multiple dimensions, including strategy, organization, and culture. To achieve organizational agility, managers must balance the exploration and exploitation of their company's resources, which often has unintended negative consequences. (Hess et al., 2016).

In fact, what deserves great attention in the practice of DT is its extremely high probability of failure. According to studies, many companies are facing challenges in developing and implementing DT strategies (Fischer et al., 2020), and about 70% of DT initiatives fail (Reeves et al., 2018). Researchers have looked into the fundamental reasons for these failures, but they have yet to reach a consensus on the factors that affect DT processes' effectiveness. The Ross et al. study, which analyzed the failures of high-profile companies, focused on the management of the transformation process and found that the root cause of ineffective DT processes was either a lack of strategic communication or a failure to provide a clear roadmap for planning and executing the required procedures (J. W. Ross et al., 2019). Addressing these problems, however, does not ensure success because, in the turbulent digital world, it is practically difficult to identify the path and final destination of digital transformation at the start (Siebel, 2019). Under such circumstances, it is necessary to find a new approach that goes beyond the limitations of the traditional strategy formulation and implementation process, which is based on strategy formulation followed by strategy implementation (Li, 2020).

In general, current knowledge implicitly assumes that once strategy is developed, implementation will automatically follow (Feurer et al., 1995). Studies also show that managers are trained to formulate strategy rather than implement it, and tend to believe that their role is to plan and think strategically, leaving implementation to those who "below" them (Hrebiniak, 2006). Or it is assumed that the strategy implementation phase begins as a continuation of the strategy formulation phase, that once a strategy has been formulated, the implementation phase comes continuously, and that there is no way to return to the formulation phase once execution has begun (Li, 2019).

Organizational reality shows that these are not always the case. In reality, strategy formulation and implementation are interdependent and should be considered as a cohesive process (J. Ross, 2020). This has important implications for the success of the DT process. Successful DT requires not only the formulation of an effective strategy, but also the ability to manage the entire transformation process in a way that allows for constant re-evaluation and adjustment of the strategy and implementation approach based on feedback received during the implementation phase to maintain consistency between strategy and execution (Beer & Eisenstat, 2000; Correani et al., 2020; Li, 2020). Unfortunately, despite the importance of this interdependent relationship between strategy formulation and implementation, there is currently a lack of empirical research and theoretical frameworks exploring this topic in DT process especially in the emerging markets (Li, 2020). Thus, there is a need for further investigation into how the strategy formulation and implementation processes work together to make DT successful.

An inescapable element in the study of strategy implementation is the issue of change management. According to a previous study, "inability to manage change"

was ranked as the number one reason for implementation failure in a large-scale survey of executives responsible for strategy implementation (Hrebiniak, 2006). Change is frequently involved in the implementation of a strategy. Strategy implementation may require modifications in work assignments, organizational structure, management methods, people, incentives, or controls. These adjustments may be critical to the success of implementation results, thus managing the change process effectively is a must in successful strategy implementation.

In examining the change management required to implement DT strategies, this paper uses the perspective of the underlying routines from which a company builds its capability. Routine and the inertia that emerges when companies create routines give an essential perspective in the study of change management (Burnes, 1996; By, 2005). Routine is a particularly important component of manufacturing capability and is an appropriate perspective for dealing with the implementation of DT strategies and associated change management in manufacturing firms (Peng et al., 2008).

Organizations with bounded rationality (or limited cognitive capacity) routinize operations as a result of their "problemistic search" activities triggered when organizational performance falls below expected levels (Argote & Greve, 2007; Cyert & March, 1963; Nelson, 1985), developing their own distinctive routines as capabilities that serve as a source of competitive advantage. These capabilities are maintained through excellence in operational routines in various areas such as product development, production processes, customer relations, or technological uniqueness (Biedenbach & Söderholm, 2008). The disadvantage of these mechanisms for generating capabilities through routinization is that it is difficult to change (Becker, 2003). Because the underlying routines are inert and hard to change, even when organizations get negative performance feedback, it is difficult to modify the capabilities that provide the competence in the existing environment (Becker, 2004). This phenomenon is known as inertia and has been studied by various scholars as a barrier to change (Miller & Chen, 1994). Inertia, according to Miller and Chen, can significantly impede adaptation and have a profound effect on performance in a novel environment.

In the context of DT, inertia has been actively discussed and studied in the IS literature since IS-embedded organizational transformation was conceptualized in the 90s (Besson & Rowe, 2012). It is continuously observed that organizations respond to these changes with rigidity and inertia and fail to implement new technologies (Haag, 2014). Thus, inertia in IS context is defined as "user attachment to, and persistence in, using an incumbent system, even if there are better alternatives or incentives to change" (Polites & Karahanna, 2012). In DT as an organizational change process, organizations must confront the inertial nature of their existing capabilities, which are the source of current competitiveness, and be able

to reorganize these capabilities to fit the changing environment and adapt to evolving digital technologies. Tushman and Romanelli also argue that rearrangement decreases inertia, thus it maintains the organization's adaptability (Tushman & Romanelli, 1985).

METHODOLOGY

This study is conducted in a manufacturing SME doing business in emerging market. There are three reasons for this. First, DT strategy implementation studies focus mainly on large firms in developed countries (Arnold et al., 2016; Li, 2020; Moeuf et al., 2020). Second, manufacturing SMEs in emerging markets play an important role in the global supply chain, and their viability and prosperity receive more attention during the supply chain crisis that followed the COVID-19 pandemic. Third, studies show that SMEs lag behind larger companies in DT, primarily because they don't have sufficient resources and time to strategically plan and implement DT (Fischer et al., 2020).

This study selected a case following the conditions. First, to fill the gap in the literature on DT strategy implementation, which is biased toward larger firms in developed countries, the organization to be used as a case must be located in an emerging market where SMEs play a significant role in the economy and supply chain and be of a size that falls within the SME category. Each country has its own definition of what constitutes an SME based on its ownership structure, number of employees, turnover and industry. This paper uses the European Commission's definition of SME, which defines SMEs as businesses with fewer than 250 employees and an annual revenue or balance sheet total not exceeding EUR 50 million or EUR 43 million, respectively. (*SME Definition*, 2023).

Second, in order to fulfill the objective of studying the process of DT strategy implementation, the company to be taken as cases must have already formulated their DT strategies and be in the implementation stage. The literature shows that SMEs often do not explicitly define innovation strategies or do not engage in strategic planning. . Therefore, the determination of whether a company had developed a DT strategy was not based on whether the DT strategy was clearly stated as a business strategy, but rather on whether management had included the implementation of DT in an action plan.

The third condition is the availability of data consistent with the research objectives. Because DT is an organizational change that affects a wide range of people, from management to frontline workers, interviews with a wide range of people at multiple organizational levels and in multiple work areas must be possible. Ethnographic observation activities and some access to operational documents, such as production records, must also be allowed, especially to gather useful data about

the change in routines and inertia that the organization experiences during DT implementation.

As a case company that satisfies these conditions, this paper focuses on an auto parts manufacturing company operating in Thailand, where the automotive industry plays a significant role in the economy. The company has 210 employees and revenues of 300 million baht (approximately 8 million euros) and meets the SME criteria described above. The company began including the use of digital technology in its business plan in 2021, and from 2022 onward, the business plan specifies key elements of Industry 4.0, the core of DT in the manufacturing industry: the introduction of IoT, use of big data, digital simulation and robotics.

The data collection is planned to be carried out with two different sources from the case company. First, qualitative data on the implementation of DT strategies will be collected by interviewing multiple organizational levels, such as top management, DT project leaders, middle managers, and lower-level managers. The interviewees were from various departments related to manufacturing operations that play a central role in the implementation of DT strategies in the manufacturing SME, such as manufacturing, production control, quality control, and production engineering.

The second data source is longitudinal project data from the beginning of the case company's DT strategy implementation process to the present. Since the company has initiated actions related to DT, empirical data will be collected on what plans were developed, with what goals, how they were implemented (or not), and with what results, through the planning documents, various records as the output from the implementation, meeting minutes, history of internal SNS and email communications, and communication records with outside firms, etc.

By analyzing the collected data from these two different sources, this study will describe detailed picture of how the case company plan and implement DT strategies to their operations, how the implemented strategies affect the routines of the people, and how and what results they had brought.

EXPECTED FINDINGS

The expected findings through this exploratory case study are the factors that influence routines to change or remain inert during the DT strategy implementation process, and the mechanisms how these factors influence / don't influence routines in the manufacturing organization (Figure 1).

Figure 1. DT strategy implementation framework

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